

Virtual campaign and messaging for disease control

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Summary

This report summarises the findings of six stakeholder workshops held on Lewis and Harris in 2023 to explore better ways to communicate with farmers on livestock disease control topics. It also describes the development of a virtual tour (VT) created in response to interest shown by the stakeholders in learning about the biosecurity measures used on Shetland.

Three elements of successful messaging were identified that lead to positive engagement with target audiences, 1) message content; 2) message formats and, 3) dissemination options.

1. In terms of message content, the work highlighted the importance of identifying the aim of messages and conveying this in clear, simple idea. The language used is extremely important. If the language is not understood it is hard for people to engage with the content of messages. Removal of confusing words increases engagement.
2. In terms of message formats, participants indicated diverse and multiple formats were preferable. Although digital formats are being encouraged to 'save trees' a printed edition can, in some places, be useful and required. To be inclusive and ensure wide engagement, the use of multiple formats should be encouraged.
3. In terms of dissemination options, creative management of dissemination campaigns can help to ensure that a message is delivered direct to the target audience.

A VT was developed to help stakeholders on Lewis and Harris explore the biosecurity procedures used in Shetland to manage livestock disease from imported animals. VTs are interactive tools which allow viewers to explore a virtual environment at their leisure, with the aim of being both entertaining and informative. The VT developed will aid in informing audiences of the importance of livestock disease control in remote places. This will initially focus on audiences in the islands and Highlands of Scotland, with the option to expand the focus in the future.

Introduction

A series of six in-person workshops on livestock disease control were held with crofters on Lewis and Harris (L&H) in November 2023. This followed on from five workshops held on L&H in 2022. Workshop locations were selected based on sheep scab hotspots identified from previous work. Five of the locations had been visited in 2022, with an location added to target new audiences.

During initial workshops held on Lewis and Harris (L&H) in 2022, participants were asked '*what does biosecurity mean to you?*'. The general response of '*nothing*' was unexpected. Crofters participating in the workshops were able to describe what could be termed as, '*good biosecurity practices*' however there was a disconnect between the term and the practices being employed. Following discussions with the ANImal HUsbandry Biosecurity Living Lab (ANIHUB) members, where this finding was discussed in depth, it was decided to alter the language to increase potential engagement. In the second set of workshops the language was changed to discuss '*disease control*' rather than '*biosecurity*'. We also made the decision to remove words that workshops participants highlighted as being '*confusing*', '*not understood*' or '*not used*'. Examples of changes in the language used by the researchers in the workshops included the following,

- Instead of 'biosecurity' the researchers discussed '(flock) disease control',
- Instead of the word 'anthelmintic(s)' researchers used the 'wormer(s)',
- Researchers avoided using the word 'fomites' as this was thought to be confusing by many of the crofters. The concept was instead described by the researchers.

Participants more readily made the connection between the phrase 'disease control' and the practices they currently did and did not employ and the researchers perceived that the crofters were engaging with the workshop with greater ease and more proactively than previous workshops. During the workshops discussions focused on message content, message formats and dissemination of messages as the three essential elements of successful messaging (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Three essential elements of successful messaging

Importance of content

Content of messages was widely discussed both with the ANIHUB group and during the L&H workshops. The main consensus was that messaging should be presented simply and clearly. Many campaigns fail in the goal of changing behaviour if the content appears to viewers to deliver an overly complex message or one that conflicts with other messaging.

Language

The language used needs to be clear and concise. Language of engagement is extremely important when preparing material for stakeholders. If the language is not understood, it is hard for people to engage fully with the content of the message. A word cloud featuring some of the terms that have led to confusion during our conversations with stakeholders was drawn together (Fig. 2). This includes words removed from presentations to increase engagement during the November 2023 workshops in L&H. These terms are routinely used when discussing sheep health and disease control, however it became clear that each time the terms were used a degree of confusion was caused in some quarters. In subsequent

workshops the terms were removed, and confusion was reduced. Engagement with the participants was perceived as higher by the researchers. We had a few discussions with participants where we mentioned we were removing the terms to help and appreciation of this was voiced.

Figure 2: Word cloud depicting words removed during crofter engagement workshops on Lewis and Harris

It is a concern when reviewing the words that are causing confusion as they are routinely used by academics, in government advice and by industry organisations. **Anthelmintics** are the chemicals used to control worm burdens in livestock, **drench check** and **reduction tests** refer to diagnostic tests for anthelmintic resistance. If these terms are poorly, or not, understood it means livestock keepers are not always understanding the problem, treatment, or diagnostic options and how to manage the situation. In the sheep scab messaging the use of the term **fomites** was still an issue. The term **biosecurity** is routinely used by stakeholders but poorly understood. The term **closed flock** appears to not have a universal definition that is accepted by all parties and relates to specific contexts and therefore farming systems. Participants were also not clear on the term **continued professional development (CPD)** and when it was explained were unwilling to accept it might/could be applied to them. When discussing training, a long conversation could be initiated around the type of training they would like to see, where and how they could

engage. Some examples of this from the workshops indicate a willingness to receive training and further their skills. Participants were keen to get information on how to use the products/treatments, e.g., how to dose correctly, how to conduct a faecal egg count (FEC) test. Crofters currently rely on watching short YouTube videos to see how to carry out tasks. Information for new entrants into crofting was requested, this can be difficult to obtain if you have no neighbours, or don't have a local network/family to draw on. Crofters mentioned this would be useful to get this from experienced/trusted crofters, a form of mentoring or peer-to-peer exchanges.

The impact of language on access to information

Searching for information on the internet can be difficult if the language used by the audience does not match that of industry messages. Web searches rely on the individual using the tagged words or metadata, or alternatively on the message provider using the language of the target audience. For example, if the keyword of the message is 'biosecurity' which the metadata identifies with, but the audience has no understanding of, or doesn't routinely use, a web search could miss important information. The researchers explored this via the following example. A web search was conducted, using the Chrome browser, for keywords routinely used to convey sheep health messages. The search returned varying numbers of results and very different initial contents depending on the term used. The exercise highlights the impact of word choice on hit rates/results (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Word search outcomes for the same request using different keywords.

Formats identified as engaging

Within the ANIHUB group potential message formats were discussed and listed (Figure 4). This list was then discussed with workshop participants in L&H to further refine the importance of the formats. The main finding from these discussions was that 'no one size fits all', a message needs to be made available in several formats.

Messaging format

- Podcasts
- Video clips
- Blogs
- Facebook posts
- Tweets
- Animations
- Infographics
- Flyers
- Posters

Figure 4. Formats identified as important for engaging target audiences and an example of how animations have been utilized in the past (Moreduun “War of the Worms”).

Digital formats are increasingly commonly used, and the amount of material that is made available via printed formats is falling, despite many people still wishing to receive messages via printed material. This was evident at the L&H workshops, where on-line links and printed materials were made available, and participants chose to take away printed materials explaining they liked to have the information ‘to hand’ rather than having to potentially search for it on a website. In addition, people with hearing issues might prefer a printed format and for people with impaired vision audio formats might be more appropriate¹. Multiple formats should be encouraged to ensure everyone can engage with messages.

Participants indicated varied, diverse choices in their preferences for formats, some preferring audio information in the form of radio or podcasts whilst others prefer visual information in the form of videos, YouTube channels or TV content. For those that learn primarily visually, formats that contain less text were chosen over lengthy text formats e.g., infographics and animations, over text heavy reports and blogs. Although blogs can engage people more than reports if they are written in an entertaining and engaging way.

Ways to disseminate

The ANIHUB and workshop participants were asked to identify ways to disseminate information to ensure they reach target audiences (Figure 5). Although this largely depends on the format, in many cases multiple formats can be disseminated together (e.g., a newspaper article can also contain links to on-line resources). By being more creative we can ensure that a message is delivered directly to the target audience, for example printing on the back of an auction mart catalogue will ensure livestock farmers can read it at convenient times. Also, if the message is on biosecurity, moving livestock, quarantine, or treating new livestock it is important to reiterate this at a timely opportunity, when livestock are being purchased and moved.

¹ Based on data from 2016

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1106562/AUK_Evidence_Pack_2021_Sept22.pdf

Messaging Dissemination

- Social media e.g. WhatsApp group, Facebook
- Local radio
- Local press e.g. Shetland Times, FIOS
- Local TV
- Agricultural papers e.g. Farmers weekly, Scottish Farmer
- Sales catalogues for the Marts
- Email alerts/notifications
- YouTube (a specific channel), linked with sheep Game and Hoof GP
- Agricultural shows
- Agricultural merchants, posters
- Website content
- Virtual Tour

Figure 5. Dissemination methods identified as important.

For remote communities, local radio, newspapers, and TV play an important role in disseminating messages. Social media is perceived to be an important method of communication but as highlighted above is only one of many formats that may be useful. Previous unpublished work demonstrated that UK farmers want information presented to them in multiple formats (Figure 6.). Online resources play a vital role in gathering material and acting as an interactive signposting element of knowledge dissemination.

Figure 6. Results from a survey understanding where farmers find information.

Virtual Tours

An interactive Virtual Tour (VT) was developed to allow stakeholders to explore the processes used in Shetland to manage livestock disease from imported animals². The VT was created in response to questions about the Shetland Animal Health Scheme (SAHS) from L&H crofters during the initial workshops.

Researchers visited Shetland to capture 360-degree footage of the infrastructure in place at the harbour and mart for sheep scab control. Subsequently, a VT was developed in collaboration with SAHS. The VT allows users to experience reality virtually, using 360-degree footage of still images and videos. It has been designed so that it can be accessed on a laptop, tablet, or smart phone and allows users to view a virtual visualisation of reality. Footage was augmented with resources allowing viewers to explore content explaining the process, e.g., links to the SAHS website. Several videos' clips have been inserted where Shetland islanders talk about the process and their opinions on 'keeping the island flocks safe'.

The link to the VT was shared with participants during the workshops. It is hoped that the VT will act as a method of communicating the process in operation on Shetland to control disease risks coming from imported animals that might be replicated in other areas (partially or fully) in the future. A Qualtrics survey embedded into the resource will collect reflections on the VT including functionality; ease of access; content and feedback on the experience. This feedback can be used to enhance further VTs.

Next Steps

- Reflections on the VT message content and format have been gathered from ANIHUB members, participants from L&H workshops and Shetland hosts on the VT and will be used to inform the development of a second VT.
- Data collected on dissemination will be used to develop the campaign for the VT and additional resources.
- Dissemination plans for the messaging campaign are being co-constructed with stakeholders in a flexible manner to create opportunities as further stakeholders are approached and engaged with.

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²To access the virtual tour please visit – <https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/shetlandlivestockvisit/>.